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MAKTABGACHA
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TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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PEDAGOGICAL METHODOLOGY IMPROVE STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL MOBILITY IN ACQUISITION OF SPECIALTY

Khidirova Muhabbat Murodillayevna

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda ixtisoslik fanlarini o'qitish har qachongidan ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda, chunki mehnat bozori har bir jamiyatda tez sur'atlar bilan o'zgarib bormoqda. Shu bois, muhandislik yo'nalishidagi talabalarning kasbiy salohiyatini oshirish uchun samarali pedagogik metod va yondashuvlarga ehtiyoj ortib bormoqda. Bundan tashqari, talabalar kasbiy harakatchanlikni anglash va rivojlantirishga yordam beruvchi pedagogik metodologiyaga muhtojdirlar. Ushbu maqolada kasbiy harakatchanlikning o'ziga xos jihatlari hamda ixtisoslikni egallash va mustahkamlashga qaratilgan metodologik yondashuvlar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik metodlar, nazariya va amaliyot, kasbiy harakatchanlik, muhandislik yo'nalishidagi talabalar.

Abstract: At present, teaching specialized subjects has become more essential than ever due to significant changes in the labor market of every society. Therefore, there is an increasing need for effective pedagogical methods and approaches to enhance the professional potential of engineering students in their respective specialties. Furthermore, students require a pedagogical methodology that helps them understand and develop professional mobility. This paper highlights the peculiarities of professional mobility and presents a specific methodology for acquiring and mastering professional competencies within a specialty.

Key words: pedagogical methods, theory and practice, professional mobility, engineering students.

Аннотация: В настоящее время преподавание специализированных дисциплин становится как никогда важным, поскольку рынок труда в любом обществе быстро меняется. Поэтому возрастает потребность в эффективных педагогических методах и подходах, направленных на повышение профессионального потенциала студентов инженерных специальностей. Кроме того, студентам необходима педагогическая методология, способствующая пониманию и развитию профессиональной мобильности. В данной статье освещаются особенности профессиональной мобильности и методологические подходы к овладению и совершенствованию профессиональных компетенций в рамках специальности.

Ключевые слова: педагогические методы, теория и практика, профессиональная мобильность, студенты инженерных специальностей.

INTRODUCTION

In the present time, the improvement of professional mobility is an important component of modern education, especially in the field of special pedagogy. Furthermore, teachers should be equipped to address the needs of students across various cultural and institutional contexts. As the demand for inclusive education grows globally, it becomes crucial to prepare future professionals to work in a wide range of settings, adapt to varying educational systems, and collaborate with local and international experts in their specialized fields. The methods used to develop professional mobility among students in special pedagogy aim to cultivate a versatile skill set, promoting not only academic knowledge but also cultural competence, communication skills, and adaptability (N.R. Saitkulova, 2024: 20–23). Pedagogical methods help engineering students demonstrate their acquired knowledge in professional mobility by exchanging ideas and information gained during their studies with experts and putting that knowledge into action in workplace practice. Moreover, cross-cultural training, internships, and the use of digital technologies also promote students' ability to reach their goals in improving professional mobility. In addition, involving students in comprehending global educational practices and challenges prepares them for inclusive education worldwide. Furthermore, pedagogical methods improve students' knowledge and fill the gaps in understanding professional mobility, which can help them advance in their specialty.

LITERATURE REVIEW

To facilitate professional mobility, several methods can be employed to enhance students' adaptability, cultural awareness, and skills. These pedagogical methods focus on creating opportunities for students to gain local and international experience, collaborate across cultures, and acquire the competencies necessary for professional development. Fieldwork and internships allow students to gain practical experience while working with experts in the field of agriculture. By engaging with different educational environments, students enhance their problem-solving abilities, cultural competence, and communication skills, which are essential for working globally (N.R. Saitkulova, 2024: 20–23). Nizamova M.N. (2024) claimed that theoretical analysis shows that the studies are consistent with each other and allow us to define personal mobility as an integral characteristic based on individual features such as activity, flexibility, and high energy reserves, manifested in behavior. Furthermore, the characteristics of personal mobility within the composition of professional mobility include activity, flexibility, the ability to change activities quickly, and readiness for self-development. Moreover, by professional mobility we mean an integrative feature that expresses the development of the ability to operate under changing conditions of professional activity, to find quick solutions in various situations, to understand professional needs, and to adapt to modern requirements (Nizamova M.N., 2022: 141–144).

It also expresses the need for future engineers to actively understand concepts related to social life, the educational environment, and professional activity; to manage changing situations; to adapt quickly; to pursue goals; to develop themselves; to establish relationships; to work with information; and to understand the content of cooperation. Furthermore, professional mobility is a combination of the ability to organize and develop professional activities, maintain a flexible mindset, and accept innovations to effectively integrate them into the process. Professional mobility implies mental activity, reflection, the ability to clarify and implement goals, as well as the ability to realize one's potential regardless of environmental or situational changes. It develops internal readiness, which combines characteristics such as high student motivation, knowledge, openness to change, adaptability to different situations, speed of thinking, curiosity, creativity, and activity. Future engineers, on the basis of model education, form a complete image of their professional mobility with personal integrative qualities and develop their worldview, level of thinking, and perception of the product of their activities. Research on the peculiarities of professional mobility was carried out by Sorokin P.A. (2005).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The modern education system requires a teacher who possesses not only high professional competence and pedagogical culture, but also individuality, creative self-development ability, a clear system of value orientations, positive motivation for teaching, and professional mobility (Vanderlinde, R., Smith, K., Murray, J., & Lunenberg, M., 2021). It should be noted that a modern university graduate must find “application” for himself in the labor market, despite the fact that one-fifth of his knowledge becomes obsolete during the first years of independent activity. This situation repeats itself throughout the entire professional career 5–10 times (Vanderlinde, R., Smith, K., Murray, J., & Lunenberg, M., 2021). Therefore, a young specialist must constantly update his knowledge and skills. Instead of the “learning for life” paradigm, the concept of “life-long learning” has emerged (Bautista, A., & Ortega-Ruiz, R., 2015).

Today, the focus on merely training a specialist is insufficient; it is crucial to pay attention to the development of a personality capable of responding flexibly to constantly changing conditions, characterized by entrepreneurial abilities, mobility, dynamism, constructiveness, and a strong sense of responsibility in professional activity (Nadia Lutsan, Olena Bulgakova, Olena Kuznetsova, Olena Babchuk, Svitlana Bykova 2024. 110).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Improving the professional mobility of engineering students requires the integration of several pedagogical theories and approaches that emphasize both technical and soft-skill development. The use of collaborative online learning platforms, such as virtual classrooms and joint international projects, enables students from different countries to work together on special education tasks, which promotes cross-cultural exchange, teamwork, and a global understanding of inclusive education. To achieve a broader knowledge base within their specialization, students must also develop proficiency in foreign languages, which allows them to communicate effectively on professional topics, particularly in areas such as agriculture and technology, and to participate confidently in international conferences and seminars. The introduction of digital tools, online courses, and e-learning resources helps engineering students stay informed about international best practices in pedagogy and special education.

Through these platforms, students can continuously update their knowledge and demonstrate their competencies in real workplace settings, thereby enhancing their professional mobility. Connecting students with

international mentors and professionals in special pedagogy further provides valuable career guidance and supports long-term professional growth. In addition, the development of key soft skills, including adaptability, problem-solving, and cross-cultural communication, is essential for students to succeed in diverse international environments where expectations, cultural norms, and teaching methods may vary. Workshops, role-playing exercises, and group projects are effective strategies to strengthen these skills and prepare students for mobility opportunities abroad. Ultimately, integrating practical experiences, cultural exposure, and international collaboration into educational programs fosters flexibility, professional readiness, and global competence among future engineers, ensuring they are well-prepared to face the challenges and seize the opportunities of working in diverse educational and professional contexts. & Svitlana Bykova, 2024, p.110).

CONCLUSION

Currently, there are significant pedagogical changes occurring in the education system, where the methods and theories of pedagogy play an essential role in engaging students to acquire specialization and develop professional mobility. Furthermore, students require specific pedagogical approaches to enhance their knowledge in their respective fields of study, particularly in the area of agriculture. Numerous theories and methods exist in pedagogy regarding how to effectively teach professional subjects. One of the key pedagogical methods is the integration of study with professional mobility – providing students with practical experience at workplaces such as factories, companies, plants, and fields. This approach bridges theoretical learning with real-world application, ensuring that students gain both academic knowledge and professional competence.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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